

Nuclear Force is Actually a Strong Gravitational Force

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we can consider atomic nucleus as a quark star. Within the nucleus protons and neutrons are in the form of different quarks and anti quarks, such that the total electrical charge of quarks is equal to the total electrical charge of the nucleus. But the total mass of the quarks is much less than the total mass of protons and neutrons within the nucleus. When each proton or neutron breaks into quark particles, there acts a strong gravitational force due to mass defect.

In microscopic view, within the nucleus there are no meaning of the terms proton and neutron, there are only quark particles. So, nucleus is congested with quarks and the temperature of the nucleus is very high of the order of 10^{12} K or more than that like quark star or neutron star. So, all quarks are at very dynamic state. For, any two same quarks $m/(qr)$ adjusted in such a way that the gravitational force dominates over electric repulsive force. Here m and q are the mass and charge of the quark respectively and r is the distance between the closest quarks. As the mass defect of the quarks is very high, the distance between the quarks is very small (10^{-54} mtr). This huge mass defect converted into binding energy according to the theory "reason behind the gravitational energy"

Within the nucleus there are three types of forces namely

Strong gravitational force due to mass defect of the quarks.

E-m force which may be attractive or repulsive depending on the set of quarks.

Force due to Fermi gas pressure.

Net effective electric repulsive force and force due to Fermi gas pressure is balanced by gravitational force.

Now, I try to give an explanation for why nucleus do not radiate its heat? We can consider that in the structure of nucleus there are two parts one is inside part which is called core which acts like a mini black hole and the other part is event horizon. Core contains more than 50% quarks and rest of the quarks rotate round the core outside the event horizon. The temperature of the core is 10^{12} K or more than it. As the core behaves like a mini black hole so, nothing can escape from it. For this reason heat can not escape from the core of the nucleus. For this reason high temperature is trapped within the core.

I predict that the radius of this core less than or equal to 10^{-55} mtr and the mass of the core is of the order 10^{-28} to 10^{-27} kg. Within the nucleus each proton has a mass defect of the order mev/c^2 . Now, recently we know that the mass of graviton is 10^{-23} ev/c^2 . Now, reason behind gravitationak energy say that mass defect converted into gravitational interaction i.e graviton. So, for Mev/c^2 mass defect there are generation of 10^{29} grviton. So, within nucleus there are vast generation of graviton. With the increase of distance this mass defect very rapidly decrease as a result number of graviton also decrease rapidly, so, the strength of interaction become weak. For this reason gravitational force within nucleus very stron but out side the nucleus very weak.

References

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